

THE GREAT TAMBURLEN AS THE PSYCHOTYPE OF THE EASTERN RULER IN THE POETRY OF CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE

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Abstract. This article claims to reveal the character of eastern monarchs and eastern medieval realities in general through the prism of such a famous English poet and playwright named Christopher Marlowe. Thus, the actual goal of the study is to study the image of the East based on the play by Marlowe: "Tamburlaine the Great". The author analyzes the correspondence of this image to the historical Tamburlaine and the East of his time; how Marlowe presents the relationship between the Eastern and European worlds, and how appropriate it is to place this play by Marlowe (and, in general, the works of his contemporaries) in the popular postcolonial discourse today.

Key words: Orientalism, postcolonial studies, English literature, Renaissance English drama, image, personality, psychotype, classical poetry, era.

The history of world literature includes the names of several outstanding writers and poets, in whose works the theme of the East is revealed so vividly and figuratively that these works have left an indelible mark on the souls of readers of different eras and times. In the history of English romanticism, this is the name of the great English poet George Gordon Byron; in German classical poetry it is the great Goethe. But few people know that this topic is also associated with the name of an outstanding representative of the English "university mind" of the reign of Queen Elizabeth I - Christopher Marlowe, who is rightfully considered the harbinger of another brilliant English poet and playwright. Renaissance William Shakespeare. Queen Elizabeth I of England (1558-1603) is the last queen of the Tudor dynasty, who ruled England from 1558 to 1603. The period from the mid-1500s to the early 1600s usually bears her name. During this period, called the Elizabethan era, English writers and poets created many of the greatest masterpieces of poetry and drama, which entered the treasury of world literature, which are deeply read and revered to this day.

A number of cultural and economic developments contributed to this remarkable literary boom of the Elizabethan era. One of the most important events occurred in 1476, when William Caxton (1422-1492) invented the printing press, established the first printing press in England, and printed the first book in English. Queen Elizabeth I of England (1558-1603) was the last monarch of the Tudor dynasty, who ruled England from 1558 to 1603. The

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The first book in this language was Recuyell of the Historyes of Troy, Caxton's translation of a popular French adventure tale. Caxton printed this book in Bruges, in present-day Belgium, around 1475. The first book printed in England was the Tales of the Philosophers, published in 1477 [6, p.322]. Printing allowed many more books to be produced at a much lower cost. The greater availability of books and their lower cost stimulated the desire of many to learn to read. As literacy increased, so did the demand for books. During the 1500s, English scholars, along with other European scholars, rediscovered the culture, philosophy, and literature of ancient Greece and Rome, which they had largely neglected during the hundreds of previous years. Translations of Greek philosophers and especially Roman literary works had a strong influence on Elizabethan writers. In addition, new literary forms were introduced into English literature. For example, English authors directly borrowed or modified such literary forms as essays from France (Michel Montaigne is the founder of this genre) and sonnets from Italy.

Another significant historical event occurred in 1588, when the English fleet defeated the Invincible Spanish Armada. This great victory caused a surge of patriotism, which was reflected in the poetry and especially in the dramaturgy of that time. Another significant event of the Elizabethan era was the fact that in 1576 James Burbage built the first theater in England called the Theater. Until this time, dramas were played out in the streets, in the houses of the nobility or palaces, as well as in English universities. After Burbage built the Theatre, other theater houses appeared, which also contributed to the rapid growth in the popularity of the drama of the Elizabeth I era, which was distinguished by new features - passion and liveliness [7, p. 317]. In this a special role belongs to a group of leading Elizabethan playwrights, who were called "university nerds" because they studied at famous English universities - Oxford or Cambridge. These playwrights included Robert Green, Christopher Marlowe and George

Peel. Christopher Marlowe was the most important playwright among the Whits, a significant figure in the dramatic genre among them in England.

Christopher Marlow (02/26/1564 - 05/30/1593) was an English playwright of the 17th century, the founder of the genre of high tragedy of the Renaissance in England. He wrote tragedies about strong personalities. He is a true representative of the art of the Renaissance, when "the ideals of individualistic humanism are clearly expressed, affirming the greatness of the earthly, human principle in all its fullness and creative activity" (1, p. 268). It is also true that the creative activity of Christopher Marlow falls at the beginning of the modern period in the history of England (1485-1603) during the reign of the Tudor dynasty and, in particular, its last representative, Elizabeth I. the initiator of the tragedy about powerful historical figures, among which is the tragedy "Tamburlaine the Great" (c. 1587). Christopher Marlowe gained his high-profile theatrical reputation from writing this very drama, Tamburlaine the Great, in which he portrayed the awe-inspiring conqueror Amir Timur, or Tamerlane the Great as he was also called, with astounding poetic prose and entertainment. The performance reflects the general admiration for the scope and limits of the human will's striving for powerful domination, which was widespread in the time of Christopher Marlowe. The liberation of the individual from medieval ascetic morality, the theomachic pathos also characterizes the tragedy "Tamburlaine the Great" (published in 1587).

A real triumph was the appearance in the theatrical season of 1587-88 of Christopher Marlowe's tragedy Tamburlaine the Great. By writing this drama, Marlowe influenced the later drama of the era, focusing on the creation of the heroic figure - the awe-inspiring conqueror and turning poetry into a flexible poetic form of tragedy. In the center of the play is a titanic personality, a person who sets ambitious goals for himself, which fit well into the spirit and letter of the Renaissance, when a person and his dignity were considered his only worthy. Accordingly, this is how Marlow paints the image of Tamburlaine: golden-haired, "tall and straight sculpted, as his desire, sublime and divine. Such large limbs, his joints as tightly knit, such broad shoulders as could be. basically conquered the burdens of Old Atlas... His arms and fingers are long and sinewy, indicative of prowess and excess of strength. In all proportions, he wanted this man to subjugate the world to Tamburlaine" [5, p.119-120].

In the drama, Tamburlaine is "an unknown Scythian, a simple shepherd" with a strong will and physical strength, striving to create a huge empire and become the ruler of the world. "Tamburlaine the Great" is the play in which Marlow

demonstrates the most consistent force, the most enduring creative force, and the most generously expended poetic resources that he masterfully wielded. This is an unusually strong and original creation, and most of the energy of the author's creativity is focused on the personality of the protagonist. Tamburlaine is the famous Timur, who ruled in Samarkand in the 14th century, conquered the Persians, Tatars, Syrians and Turks, and only death prevented him from fighting the Chinese. In Marlowe's play, it is a Scythian shepherd who has achieved greatness due to his character, followed by courageous and determined men, loved by a beautiful and kind woman who always wins. It may seem that these are not the strokes of which a great drama is built, for one may ask what is the vital element of the conflict, if not in the simple confrontation (repeated in many episodes) of one side against the other. But the conflict in the drama Tamburlaine the Great takes a special form, including reactions and judgments. The Prologue says: "Look, but his image is in this tragic glass", "and then applaud his luck as you like" [5, p.105]. There is a characteristic note of challenge in this, since soon the question arises for both the audience and the characters themselves how the fate of this conqueror should be considered:

What god, or villain, or spirit of the earth,
Or the monster turned into a manly form,
... It grows from earth, hell or heaven. [5, p.131]

This is the question that Ortigius asks at the beginning of the play (act 2, scene 6), and he firmly directs our attention to the conflict of the judges, which is fundamental. For Christian judgment must tell the audience that the fate of this man is not to be applauded at all; however, the drama helps to counteract this and gain admiration from those whose values are opposed to those of Christianity. The protagonist is a fighter with great ambition and great vitality. He pours out his soul in the long, pathos-filled monologues that Christopher Marlowe introduced into the arsenal of Elizabethan drama. The poet saw the true origins of the tragic character not in the external circumstances that determine his fate, but in the internal spiritual contradictions that torn apart this truly gigantic personality, rising above the ordinary and generally accepted norms: already in Tamburlaine's Prologue. Magnificently, the author's desire to pave new paths in dramatic art is noticed in order to intrigue the public with images of world-historical events, pictures of the fall of kingdoms and peoples.

Summing up, it should be noted that Christopher Marlowe was the first who tried to put the action of the drama on a psychological basis, to comprehend it with internal motives. And for this he chose the image of an eastern ruler. In the

person of Tamburlaine, he revealed the type of ambitious man, seized by an insatiable thirst for power; Tamburlaine is used only with a passion for conquest. At the same time, he is a living person, capable of love. But even in love dreams next to the woman he loves, he indulges in dreams of future power. Tamburlaine's monologues are devoted to reflections on the greatness and beauty of man. In battles, he is cruel and merciless. And even knowing that death awaits him, he continues the battle and wants to subordinate both illness and death to his will. He wants to conquer even the natural course of things. The writer sees the unity of tragedy in the fact that all faces are brought in connection with this tragic character trait of the Eastern conqueror, they rise and die through it.

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